

945358-BIGPICTURE
Central Repository for Digital Pathology

WP2 - Infrastructure and database hosting

D2.04 - Report on status of pilot services implementation

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Document History

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Abstract

This report documents findings from ongoing work in Task 2.5 Pilot operation and Task 2.6 Iterative development that has been carried out since the establishment of the pilot system which itself was described in D2.02 Report on the pilot system establishment.

WP2 has implemented data submission service interfaces. For data transfer the interfaces between Finland and Sweden differ at the moment. Finland provides an SFTP interface, and Sweden provides an S3 object storage protocol based interface, and users can choose to use either, according to their own preference, as data is mirrored after submission.

Metadata submission (programmatic) interface has been developed based on the metadata schema. The data submission tools are implemented in various organisations. The XML files are stored in the data repository for further usage.

In the future the focus will be on metadata utilisation, i.e., the service integrations in the repository. In particular, the discovery services will be developed in collaboration with the data providers and the future users. The feature set and functionalities will be limited to what the data contributors deem appropriate, given how they have structured their data collection and what assumptions have been made in their privacy preservation measures.

Methods

This deliverable describes the work done regarding the pilot version of the infrastructure receiving test data, and anonymous data. In Task 2.5, which is on-going until Feb 2023, the project plans to collect and upload up to 0.5 PB of data.

The establishment of the Bigpicture repository pilot system was carried out in Task 2.03 Pilot system development and described in D2.02 Report on the pilot system establishment. The pilot system was then iteratively improved as part Task 2.06 Iterative development.

The iterative improvement of the pilot services is carried out using Scrum methodology, in short-cycle sprints to meet tactical priorities defined in lower-frequency requirement dialogue, which is primarily carried out in the Bigpicture task forces.

This work was carried out initially by two Scrum teams; one at CSC in Finland, and one at UU in Sweden. However, during the spring of 2022, the WP2 academic partners carried out a reorganisation of their sensitive data service development teams, effectively doubling their resource contribution to this effort, which at the time of writing comprises four Scrum teams; one at each of LIU and UU, and two at CSC. The reorganisation was necessitated by the fact that a new Scrum team was established at LIU and brought into the effort, and that further personnel were brought into the Scrum team at CSC, which had to be split in two in order to maintain an effective agile team size, of about 5 people per team. This resource expansion was made possible in part because challenges in recruitment were much lessened in the later waves of the coronavirus pandemic. The orderly transition into the new way of organising work in WP2 took significant effort, however the transition was deemed necessary in order to be able to make effective use of the increased resources, and to maintain effective pace in the project.

In Scrum methodology, one or more scrum teams work to iteratively improve a product in short development sprints, with high degrees of autonomy, based on priorities defined by the product owner. The product owner is tasked with understanding stakeholder needs, and - based on this understanding - maintaining a prioritised backlog of discrete desirable improvements for the product, that the Scrum teams can then take on and implement. The backlog is discussed with stakeholders at designated sprint review meetings, where backlog items are refined and broken down into smaller items, which are better understood and more easily taken on by the teams for independent implementation.

The Bigpicture repository infrastructure is being developed based on existing ELIXIR production service software for sensitive personal data, which the data hosting organisations CSC and UU are already providing as national services to the research communities in Finland and Sweden, and maintains and further iteratively develops for these communities using Scrum methodology.

The WP2 lead from LIU is the appointed Scrum product owner for the purposes of developing the Bigpicture repository infrastructure, and is tasked with maintaining the prioritised product backlog for development of the Bigpicture WP2 repository infrastructure. The Bigpicture repository infrastructure is generally maintained at a higher level of abstraction, as nearest-term priorities are transferred to the product backlogs for the national sensitive data services for more autonomous implementation by the national Scrum teams.

For the purposes of translating stakeholder needs into backlog items, the product owners of the Bigpicture repository infrastructure and the Finnish and Swedish national sensitive data services engage in several Bigpicture task forces. They also engage in the Bigpicture WP2 management team, which is chaired by the WP2 lead from LIU. Additionally, all Bigpicture beneficiaries are welcome to attend product owner sync meetings and WP2 management meetings as observers to contribute to the discussions.

The Bigpicture repository infrastructure development backlog is discussed and refined in weekly product owners sync meetings, as preparation for decision making in WP2 management, and to prepare for backlog refinements and sprint planning in the national sensitive data services development teams.

The prerequisite to receive data is that it conforms to the mandatory submission metadata, which has been developed by Data Contributors in WP3, based on cross work package discussions in the Metadata Task Force. To better understand specific requirements and preferences regarding the submission interfaces, WP2 set up a dedicated meeting with staff at spear heading data contributors tasked with hands-on data submission.

Various processes regarding data submission, user registration and their role in their organisations have been modelled in cross work package discussion in the biweekly Architecture Task Force led by WP2.

Results

Data submission

The first pilots of data submission were done during the reporting period. The submission process was piloted with several data contributors (of WP3). Data contributors developed the first version of metadata model for imaging data and in collaboration with them. Work package 2 developed the Metadata submission API¹.

The Metadata submission API enables submission and validation of metadata files, which are associated with the uploaded image files. The Metadata submission API is connected to data ingestion workflow that:

- User creates submission (with JSON body)
- User creates study object (with XML file/JSON)
- User creates image object (with XML file)
- User creates bpdataset object (with XML file)

¹<https://editor.swagger.io/?url=https://raw.githubusercontent.com/CSCfi/metadata-submitter/develop/docs/specification.yml>

- User adds Datacite info (with JSON)
- User publishes submission

Figure 1 summarises the technical design. The Bigpicture repository will further process the metadata for storing the datasets, the discovery and for the metadata access management. Dataset gets an identifier, which is used to refer to the related metadata and image files. By default, all datasets receive Data Object Identifiers from DataCite. The generation of these identifiers is launched by a submission of an image.xml file. Synchronisation of the identifiers between Bigpicture repositories has been planned but not implemented.

Different tools can be developed for the upload. One option investigated is how a web interface (Figure 2) being developed for genomic data submission could be used for image data submission. Currently, data transfer protocols are different in Bigpicture repositories in Finland and Sweden. This offers more variety for the users. There is support command line transfer. Encryption with the repository's public key is an essential step.

Further development

Part of the metadata is inside DICOM files among the image, but part of the metadata, which is still being defined in Metadata TF, will be in the submitted XML files. It has to be defined, which of the metadata would be part of the granted data for the user.

Due to the federated nature of BIGPICTURE repositories, mirroring metadata and synchronising the identifiers between the repositories are essential questions to solve in the future.

Also, the discovery service logic and interface are being discussed within the project. The selected subset of the metadata that can be indexed to the discovery metadata.

The future steps by project month 24 (Feb 2023) are to receive more data and to receive data from more data contributors. Inference model execution will be developed to produce metadata for images. This may be used in the discovery or data interpretation. Metadata model will be continuously reviewed and thus data repository has to adapt to it. Development work for data repository interfaces and processes will continue. Especially discovery service and metadata access for the researcher will be investigated with the data contributors since there must be an agreement which data is exposed where. Data mirroring will be enhanced and the services will be set up for the availability in both data centres.

Conclusion

As a result of the activities described above, on 2022-06-03, Bigpicture partner RÖ uploaded the first clinical dataset compliant to the current Bigpicture metadata standard to the Bigpicture repository using the data submission API. Shortly thereafter, on 2022-06-23, Bigpicture partner MUW successfully submitted the second clinical dataset compliant to the current Bigpicture metadata standard using the same procedure. For the final information on these datasets please consult deliverable report D3.03.

Several data submission tools that can use the metadata submission API are being developed in different work packages.

The Architecture task force has been the important discussion forum regarding various processes concerning data submission, user registration and their role in their organisations.

Figure 1: Data submission process diagram. Metadata is submitted via API and data transferred to another interface (SFTP or S3). Please use zoom to view.

Figure 2: A possibility to use a web interface developed for genomic data submission is being explored.

Annex 1 - Draft user documentation

Data submission API

Command line user interface for the Sensitive Data Archive: <https://github.com/NBISweden/sda-cli/>

Finnish data submission has also a client called SDA. There is a command-line client or graphical version. <https://github.com/CSCfi/sda-uploader>

Metadata submission tools will have their own user guides. For the tool developers WP2 offer support and API is documented via Swagger web pages.